

Collection of phytoplanktons and zooplanktons on four lakes of Laguna

Rheem B. Balindong^{1*}, Daniel D. Geda¹, Cecilia S. Cordero²

¹Biology Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

²School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: rbbalindong@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

*Seven lakes of San Pablo, Laguna were formed by a unique process called a phreatic explosion caused by steam derived groundwater. This is a one-day study done during February 7, 2017 between 8:00 am and 3:00 pm by conducting water sample in the middle of four lakes to compare the physicochemical parameters of the water and determine the presence of phytoplankton and zooplankton in each lake. It was found out that the water parameters of each lake were similar with differences and the phytoplanktons *Synedra* sp. and *Pediastrum* sp. were present and the most dominant in each lake. The similarities of the lake may be attributed to the similar environments of the lake, but the difference is influenced by the direct surroundings that differ in each lake.*

Keywords: *Lakes; Zooplankton; Phytoplankton; Physicochemical parameters.*

To cite this article:

Balindong, R. B., Geda, D. D., & Cordero, C. S. (2021). Collection of phytoplanktons and zooplanktons on four lakes of Laguna. *SDCA Journal of Biological Research*, 2, 6-9.

Introduction

According to Lindsey and Scott (2010), planktons are wandering microscopic organisms that live in fresh or marine water environments. They also said that it can be divided into phytoplanktons and zooplanktons. Phytoplanktons are similar to terrestrial plants because they contain chlorophyll, and they can do photosynthesis. They are the primary producers in the aquatic ecosystem. Sakset and Chankaew (2013) said that phytoplanktons have been used as bioindicators for pollution because phytoplanktons are sensitive to environmental changes. Zooplanktons are microscopic organisms that also wander near the surface in aquatic waters. They can be classified as temporary zooplankton and permanent zooplankton (Brillo, 2016). The temporary zooplankton is plankton, usually the larval forms of aquatic animals and insects (MarineBio Conservation Society, n.d.). According to Ismail and Adnan (2016), zooplanktons are an important food sources to aquatic organisms. Rahkola-Sorsa (2008) said that zooplanktons can also be used as a tool for determining the ecological status of the lake because zooplankton community structure is characterized by intrinsic factors such as surface area, depth, trophic level, color of the water, and the biological community of the lake (as cited in Voutilainen et al., 2016; Dalpadedo et al., 2020).

Materials and Methods

Study Area

According to the Laguna Lake Development Authority, the seven freshwater lakes of San Pablo, Laguna were formed when the lava from Mt. Cristobal met groundwater, which blew out the rocks forming craters that were later filled with rainwater. Lake Calibato is the deepest of the seven lakes with a depth of 156 m, and it supplies the city and neighboring towns with an abundant number of fish. Lake Yambo and Lake Pandin are considered a twin lake due to their trophic state which is oligotrophic, and these lakes are two of the tourist destinations and suitable for swimming, picnic, and outing of San Laguna. Lake Pandin

is said to be the most pristine of the seven lakes of San Pablo. Lake Mohicap is one of the main source of water in the city and supplier of tilapia for Metro Manila.

Water Sampling

Sampling was done on February 7, 2017 between 8:00 am and 3:00 pm. Water samples were taken in the middle of each lake. A zooplankton net was used to collect zooplanktons; the collected samples were then placed in a sealed plastic bottle and ethanol was added to each sample in order to preserve the samples. For the collection of phytoplankton, water was collected in a sealed plastic bottle and Lugol's solution was added in order to preserve the samples. Water was also collected underwater in amber bottles, and it was made sure that there were no bubbles present in the collected water in order to determine the dissolved oxygen content of each lake.

Water Physicochemical Parameters

For the physical parameters, the temperature, transparency, and the geographical coordinates of each lake was taken during sampling. For the temperature, a digital pH meter that can also measure temperature was used. For transparency, a 30 cm secchi disk was used and determined in situ. For the geographical coordinates, a Global Positioning System (GPS) was used. For the chemical parameters, the dissolved oxygen and pH of each lake was taken. For the dissolved oxygen, the amber bottle used in collecting it was shattered so it was not included. For the pH, a digital pH meter was used.

Phytoplankton and Zooplankton Identification

Slides were prepared using the water samples collected from each lake mixed with Lugol's solution and ethanol. The slides were observed using a compound light microscope in order to see the specimens that were collected. The specimens were identified morphologically until genus level, however since the specimens were not verified by an expert, the identification may not be accurate.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. The physicochemical parameters of the different lakes

Parameters	Lake Mohicap	Lake Palakpakin	Lake Pandin	Lake Calibato
pH	11.3	10.5	11.15	11.1
Temperature	26.5°C	25.0°C	25.5°C	23.5°C
Coordinates	N14°07.334 E121°20.1	E121°20.217	N14°06.760 E121°87.895	E121°22.601 N14°06.310
Transparency	1.15 & 0.9 = 1.025 m	1.45 & 1.2 = 1.325 m	1.1 & 1.6 = 1.35 m	1 & 1.6 = 1.3 m

The table above shows the results of the physicochemical parameters of the different lakes that were sampled. The pH of the lakes are close to each other, with the pH of Lake Palakpakin being the lowest with a pH of 10.5. According to the Fondriest Environmental Inc. (2013), the pH of a lake is important because not only can it affect the organisms living in or near the lake, but it can also affect the toxicity and solubility of heavy metals found in the lake. However, there are variations in the pH of the lake due to the amount of carbon dioxide that will be present due to photosynthesis and the environmental conditions such as the amount of precipitation. The temperature of the lakes are close to each other like with the pH. According to the Fondriest Environmental Inc. (2014), the temperature of the lake is important because it can influence the other parameters as well as alter the physical and chemical properties of the lake. The transparency was measured using a secchi disk and the average of the two measurement was computed in order to get the turbidity of the different lakes. The Lake Mohicap is the most turbid because the secchi disk can only be seen in around 1 m, while in the other lakes the secchi disk can be seen deeper, which is around 1.3 m. Lake Mohicap is the least transparent meaning it has the greatest number of phytoplanktons, zooplanktons, and suspended mineral particles (Boyd, 2016).

Table 2. Tabulation of phytoplankton and zooplankton in seven lakes

Lake Mohicap	Lake Palakpakin	Lake Pandin	Lake Calibato
<i>Anabaena sp.</i>	<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i>	<i>Anabaena sp.</i>	<i>Chlorococcum sp.</i>
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i>	<i>Chlorococcus sp.</i>	<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i>	<i>Chlorococcus sp.</i>
<i>Closterium sp.</i>	<i>Cyclotella sp.</i>	<i>Euglena sp.</i>	<i>Closterium sp.</i>
<i>Cocconeis sp.</i>	<i>Cymbella sp.</i>	<i>Pediastrum sp.</i>	<i>Pediastrum sp.</i>
<i>Cryptomonas sp.</i>	<i>Navicula sp.</i>	<i>Staurastrum sp.</i>	<i>Scenedesmus sp.</i>
<i>Pediastrum sp.</i>	<i>Pandorina sp.</i>	<i>Synedra sp.</i>	<i>Synedra sp.</i>
<i>Peridinium sp.</i>	<i>Pediastrum sp.</i>		Copepod
<i>Shoederia sp.</i>	<i>Peridinium sp.</i>		
<i>Synedra sp.</i>	<i>Scenedesmus sp.</i>		
	<i>Suriella elegans</i>		
	<i>Synedra sp.</i>		

The table above shows the presence of phytoplanktons and zooplanktons in each lake of San Pablo, Laguna. The different lakes have mostly similar organisms; however, most organisms were seen at Lake Palakpakin. It may mean that Lake Palakpakin was the most diverse compared to other lakes. *Synedra sp.* and *Pediastrum sp.* are the most abundant species as these can be seen in all the lakes evaluated. The species present in the table is not the only species present in each lake; there may be other species present but was not seen. Lake Calibato was the only one seen with a zooplankton, which is a copepod. The same can be said that it does not necessarily mean that the other lakes do not have zooplankton present or that copepods are the only zooplankton present in Lake Calibato.

Conclusion

The different lakes that were sampled namely, Lakes Calibato, Mohicap, Palakpakin, and Pandin have similar physicochemical parameters as well as the phytoplankton present. Different lakes may have

the comparable properties, however there are also differences due to having different surroundings which can contribute to numerous factors.

References

- Boyd, C. E. (2016, January 4). *Phytoplankton a crucial component of aquaculture pond ecosystems*. Global Seafood Alliance. <https://www.globalseafood.org/advocate/phytoplankton-a-crucial-component-of-aquaculture-pond-ecosystems/>
- Brillo, B. B. C. (2016). Development of a small lake: Ecotourism enterprise for Pandin lake, San Pablo City, Philippines. *Lakes & Reservoirs: Research & Management*, 21(4), 284-292. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lre.12150>
- Dalpadado, P., Arrigo, K. R., van Dijken, G. L., Skjoldal, H. R., Bagøien, E., Dolgov, A. V., Prokopchuk, I. P., & Sperfeld, E. (2020). Climate effects on temporal and spatial dynamics of phytoplankton and zooplankton in the Barents Sea. *Progress in Oceanography*, 185, 102320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2020.102320>
- Fondriest Environmental, Inc. (2014, October 22). *Algae, phytoplankton and chlorophyll*. Fundamentals of Environmental Measurements. <https://www.fondriest.com/environmental-measurements/parameters/water-quality/algae-phytoplankton-chlorophyll/>
- Ismail, A. H., & Adnan, A. A. M. (2016). Zooplankton composition and abundance as indicators of eutrophication in two small man-made lakes. *Tropical Life Sciences Research*, 27(supp1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.21315/tlsr2016.27.3.5>
- Lindsey, R., & Scott, M. (2010, July 13). *What are phytoplankton?* NASA Earth Observatory. <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/features/Phytoplankton>
- MarineBio Conservation Society. (n.d.). *Zooplankton*. <https://www.marinebio.org/creatures/zooplankton/>
- Rahkola-Sorsa, M. (2008). *The structure of zooplankton communities in large boreal lakes and assessment of zooplankton methodology* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Joensuu). UEF eRepository. https://erepo.uef.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/8712/urn_isbn_978-952-219-201-1.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Sakset, A., & Chankaew, W. (2013). Phytoplankton as a bio-indicator of water quality in the freshwater fishing area of Pak Phanang River Basin (Southern Thailand). *Chiang Mai Journal of Science*, 40(3), 344-355. <https://www.thaiscience.info/Journals/Article/CMJS/10886443.pdf>
- Voutilainen, A., Jurvelius, J., Lilja, J., Viljanen, M., & Rahkola-Sorsa, M. (2016). Associating spatial patterns of zooplankton abundance with water temperature, depth, planktivorous fish and chlorophyll. *Boreal Environmental Research*, 21, 101-114. <https://helda.helsinki.fi/bitstream/handle/10138/225337/ber21-1-2-101.pdf?sequence=1>